

Does Blooket Support Quiz Preparation? Exploring Students' Experiences with Game-Based Science Review

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Abstract

Using a convergent mixed-methods descriptive survey design, this study examined secondary students' experiences with Blooket for integrated science quiz review. Participants (N = 46) completed a researcher-developed questionnaire comprising a five-point Likert-scale items assessing engagement, motivation, perceived learning and quiz readiness, feedback and metacognitive support, technical ease/access, classroom climate, fairness/alignment with content, and overall acceptance, along with open-ended questions on benefits, challenges, and suggested improvements. Quantitative results indicated generally favorable perceptions across all dimensions, including strong endorsement of Blooket as a useful review approach and willingness to use it again before quizzes. Qualitative findings converged with these results, highlighting enjoyment, sustained attention, immediate corrective feedback, and repeated exposure to questions as key benefits supporting confidence and preparation. Students also identified implementation constraints, particularly time pressure, question-format concerns, competitive stress for some learners, and the need for clearer explanations after incorrect responses. Overall, students viewed Blooket as a highly acceptable platform for science review, with findings underscoring the importance of pacing, item clarity, and brief debriefing routines to strengthen learning value and equitable participation.

Keywords: *blooket, gamification, science review, student perceptions, mixed-methods survey.*

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Introduction

Science education is widely recognized as a cornerstone of scientific literacy, critical thinking, and informed participation in contemporary society. Within STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics), many nations now position STEM education as a strategic priority for developing twenty-first century competencies, including computational, critical, and creative thinking, and for preparing learners to address complex real-world challenges in areas such as energy, the environment, and health (Li et al., 2016; Martín-Páez et al., 2019; Struyf et al., 2019; Wahono et al., 2020; The White House, 2018; Kayan-Fadlelmula et al., 2022). Yet, sustaining students' interest in school science remains difficult. Traditional, teacher-centered instruction is often described as monotonous, constrained in hands-on practice, and limited in opportunities for complex problem-solving due to time and resource barriers (Gao et al., 2020; Klopfer & Thompson, 2020). Comparable challenges have been documented in Indonesian junior high school science, where students frequently perceive lessons as difficult and dull, resulting in low motivation and passive participation, particularly during concept-heavy review before tests (Hakim et al., 2024; Nuraysha et al., 2024). These concerns have intensified calls for instructional approaches that make STEM learning more engaging, practice-oriented, and responsive to students' needs.

One prominent response has been the expanded use of digital technologies and game-based learning. Integrating information and communication technology (ICT) can support more interactive lessons, accommodate diverse learning styles, and encourage greater learner autonomy and responsibility (Mahdum et al., 2019; Ningsih et al., 2021; Junaidi et al., 2020). Park and Park (2021) report that game-based learning is a promising strategy for increasing engagement and motivation and supporting learning outcomes in early childhood contexts. Documented benefits span cognitive, social, emotional, and behavioral domains, and commonly include gains in higher-order thinking, problem-solving ability, teamwork, creativity, and digital literacy skills. Drawing on Kukulska-Hulme et al. (2021) and Ishak et al. (2021), DGBL is increasingly described as a global, contemporary approach to teaching and learning, with particular potential value for STEM relative to conventional methods. Ball et al. (2020), Ishak et al. (2021), Kayan-Fadlelmula et al. (2022), and Klopfer and Thompson (2020) argue that digital educational games can immerse learners in challenge-based, simulated tasks with built-in support, enabling practice in problem solving and critical thinking while sustaining motivation and enjoyment. DGBL is not uniformly effective. Halpern et al. (2012) demonstrate that educational games can enhance motivation and reasoning. Johnson and Mayer (2010) report learning benefits in game-like multimedia contexts. Masek et al. (2017) show that integrating video games can improve mathematics mastery. Wu and Anderson (2015) similarly highlight that technology-enhanced STEM instruction can support learning outcomes when appropriately designed. DGBL does not reliably outperform traditional approaches. Renken and Nunez (2013) show that interactivity alone does not ensure conceptual learning. Riopel et al. (2019) report variable effects of serious games on science achievement. Wang (2020) adds that weak game design can increase cognitive load and hinder learning. Meta-analytic evidence has begun to accumulate by domain. Riopel et al. (2019) synthesize serious-game effects in science. Tsai and Tsai (2020) meta-analyze digital game-based science learning. Byun and Joung (2018) and Tokac et al. (2019) do the same for mathematics. Wang et al. (2022) examine achievement effects across STEM more broadly. However, these reviews often emphasize single subject areas or narrow outcome categories, leaving an incomplete account of DGBL's multifaceted influence across STEM education. This conclusion is consistent with broader work on digital

platforms underscoring that technology-based media are increasingly central to effective learning activities when thoughtfully implemented (Fatoni et al., 2024).

Studies across platforms suggest that integrating game-like digital features can deepen engagement and improve learning. Iman et al. (2021) report higher participation using game-based systems. Aynsley et al. (2018) document positive learning support via Braincept. Perera and Hervás-Gómez (2021) similarly highlight Socrative's value for interactive learning across disciplines. These platforms commonly use fun, challenge, and competition to capture attention while providing immediate feedback that supports learning and sustains motivation (Iman et al., 2021). In addition, collaborative affordances in interactive platforms can strengthen peer communication and cooperation, which may further support engagement and understanding (Asniza et al., 2021).

Against this backdrop, gamification has emerged as a widely adopted design approach. Gamification is commonly defined as the integration of game-like elements, such as points, badges, levels, leaderboards, and rewards, into non-game contexts to increase motivation and goal completion (Saleem et al., 2022; Lopez et al., 2019). While game-based learning emphasizes full games designed for educational purposes (Kim et al., 2009), gamification selectively embeds game elements into existing activities to enhance engagement. In educational contexts, gamification has been linked to higher participation in online discussions, stronger motivation to engage with review materials, and improved understanding (Barata et al., 2017). Since rising to prominence around 2010, gamification has expanded into a highly influential field, with recent work characterizing it as a modern technological innovation for improving learning quality (Cavus et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2023; Cabello et al., 2021; Dahalan et al., 2024; Krath et al., 2021).

Across subject areas, empirical work indicates that gamification can strengthen motivation, participation, and engagement. Game elements have been associated with greater interest in learning, healthy competition, and improvements in digital literacy (Hanafiah & Teh, 2019; Mahbubi, 2025; Sari & Alfiyan, 2023). However, research has often concentrated on specific fields such as chemistry, biology, and language learning, and systematic investigations of particular gamified platforms in junior high school science remain comparatively limited (Quyen et al., 2025; Hanafiah & Teh, 2019; Mahbubi, 2025). This gap is especially visible for Blooket in Indonesian lower secondary science, where the evidence base is only beginning to emerge (Sari & Alfiyan, 2023; Astuti, 2025).

Digital game-based learning has also been associated with more attractive, interactive, and student-centred instruction. Digital games can capture learners' interest, promote interaction, and support the development of language and content knowledge (Ahmed et al., 2022; Lilić & Bratož, 2019; Prayudi et al., 2021; Susanti & Trisnawati, 2019). These findings complement ICT literature emphasizing that digital tools can enhance learning quality and support students' technological proficiency (Mahdum et al., 2019; Ningsih et al., 2021; Junaidi et al., 2020). In science education, gamification-based applications such as Blooket are increasingly discussed as promising innovations that combine visualization, game elements, and competition to create more engaging learning environments for junior high school students (Hidayatullah et al., 2023; Arianto et al., 2024). Among gamified quiz platforms (e.g., Wordwall, Quizizz, Kahoot), Blooket has attracted attention as a flexible, web-based tool. It has been described as a free platform that allows teachers to design curriculum-aligned activities, including assessments and practice tasks organized by subject, grade level, and theme

(Sartika et al., 2023). The platform incorporates core gamification elements such as points, leaderboards, levels, and badges to foster intrinsic motivation and enjoyment (Sartika et al., 2023; Thu & Dan, 2023). It is accessible via [blooket.com](https://www.blooket.com) without installation; teachers host games through accounts (often linked to Google), and students join using a code or QR code without creating individual accounts (Nugroho, 2022; Sartika et al., 2023).

Thu and Dan (2023) and Wenjing Huang (2022) note that Blooket offers multiple arcade-style modes (e.g., Gold Quest, Fishing Frenzy, Tower Defense, Battle Royale, Crazy Kingdom) that draw on the same question set but vary in gameplay mechanics and pacing. This design aims to reduce repetitiveness by allowing the same content to be encountered through varied challenges. Blooket also provides immediate feedback: responses are automatically checked, results are recorded, and students see performance in real time, enabling them to track progress, adjust strategies, and recognize their achievements (Bratel et al., 2021; Wongsaming et al., 2023; Sartika et al., 2023). These features suggest potential not only for engagement but also for metacognitive monitoring and self-regulated learning in review contexts. Existing evidence generally portrays Blooket as engaging and beneficial. Studies in vocabulary and language learning report gains in mastery and positive student perceptions of Blooket as an effective learning medium (Kinanti & Sari, 2024; Isyamirahim et al., 2024; Susilo et al., 2022; Sartika et al., 2023). Students often describe increased participation and attention, a more enjoyable learning experience, and easier use compared with some alternatives (Pham & Ly, 2023; Thu & Dan, 2023; Le, 2020; Faruq & Amri, 2023; Kuzma, 2022). Nonetheless, studies also identify constraints such as internet connectivity, unequal device access, and the possibility that highly competitive modes may be stressful or discouraging for some learners (Nappe, 2023; Nabila & Nurhamidah, 2024; Thu & Dan, 2023).

More recently, research has begun to examine Blooket in science education. In an Indonesian junior high school context, Astuti (2025) reported that Blooket use in natural science (IPA) increased motivation, strengthened conceptual understanding, and improved social interaction during class activities. Gamification elements, including points and leaderboards, helped create a competitive yet enjoyable atmosphere that encouraged previously passive students to participate more actively and develop confidence (Astuti, 2025). Blooket-based interactive assessments were also reported to improve learning outcomes and provide teachers with real-time insight into students' strengths and weaknesses, supporting responsive follow-up instruction (Astuti, 2025). These findings complement earlier evidence that well-designed gamification can enhance motivation and achievement when integrated thoughtfully into teaching (Hanafiah & Teh, 2019; Mahbubi, 2025; Sari & Alfian, 2023).

The potential of Blooket to support science learning is also consistent with several theoretical perspectives. Constructivist theory emphasizes learners' active knowledge construction through interaction; Blooket's game-based activities provide opportunities to engage with content, receive feedback, and reflect on understanding in interactive settings (Bustomi et al., 2024; Bada & Olusegun, 2015). Motivation theory, including Bandura's concept of self-efficacy, suggests that repeated successful experiences can strengthen confidence and persistence, which may be supported through iterative game challenges (Bandura & Hall, 2018; Astuti, 2025). Technology-based learning perspectives further propose that platforms offering real-time performance data can enhance instructional quality by providing timely evidence of progress (Aisyah et al., 2024). Finally, Vygotskian accounts highlight social interaction

as a driver of learning; Blooket's team modes and opportunities for in-game discussion may support cooperation, peer explanation, and a positive classroom climate (Hogan & Tudge, 2014; Astuti, 2025).

Despite these promising developments, important gaps remain. Much of the Blooket literature has concentrated on language learning and vocabulary acquisition, often relying on pre–post designs and broad satisfaction measures (Isyamirahim et al., 2024; Susilo et al., 2022; Kinanti & Sari, 2024; Sartika et al., 2023). Although early evidence in Indonesian science classrooms indicates positive effects on motivation and conceptual learning (Astuti, 2025), systematic investigation of students' experiences of Blooket as a science review tool across multiple dimensions remains limited, particularly beyond single-site studies. DGBL effects in STEM are not consistent across settings and depend heavily on design and implementation. Riopel et al. (2019) report variable outcomes for serious games in science. Tsai and Tsai (2020) likewise find mixed effects in digital game-based science learning. Wang et al. (2022) show similar variability for STEM achievement, supporting the need for context-sensitive work that centers learners' perspectives on engagement, learning, and classroom dynamics. In addition, much of the Blooket literature concentrates on language learning and relies heavily on pre–post designs or broad perception measures, leaving fewer studies that document how students experience Blooket specifically as a science review tool across multiple dimensions of use and perception. To address these gaps, this study examined secondary students' experiences using Blooket in integrated science review sessions through three research questions:

1. What is the students' demographic and Blooket-use profiles for science review?
2. To what extent do students perceive Blooket as an effective science review tool?
3. What benefits, challenges, and improvements do students report regarding Blooket for science review?

Materials and Methods

This study employed a convergent mixed-methods descriptive survey design to document secondary students' experiences with Blooket during integrated science quiz-review sessions. Data were gathered in the first semester of SY 2025–2026 from Grades 9–12 students who had participated in Blooket-based review activities. A census approach was used within the study setting: all eligible students across Grades 9–12 were invited to participate. Participation was voluntary, responses were treated confidentially, and findings were reported only in aggregate, with qualitative comments presented in anonymized form.

Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire consisting of (a) a brief profile section (grade level, gender, and patterns of Blooket use such as game modes and teaming format), (b) Likert-type items assessing perceptions of Blooket-supported science review across key dimensions—engagement, motivation, perceived learning/quiz readiness, feedback and self-monitoring, usability and access, classroom dynamics (competition and collaboration), fairness/alignment, and overall acceptance—and (c) open-ended prompts eliciting students' perceived benefits, challenges, and suggested improvements. Prior to administration, the instrument underwent face and content validation through expert review, and revisions were made to strengthen clarity, developmental appropriateness, and alignment between items and the study constructs.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study findings, beginning with a profile of students' Blooket use during integrated science review, followed by their survey-based perceptions across key dimensions, and concluding with qualitative themes describing reported benefits, challenges, and suggested improvements.

Research Question 1: What is the students' demographic and Blooket-use profiles for science review

Table 1. Grade Level of Student Respondents (N = 46)

Grade Level	n	%
9	20	43
10	19	41
11	3	7
12	4	9

The respondent pool was heavily concentrated in Grades 9 and 10 (84%), with comparatively few students from Grades 11 and 12 (16%). This distribution indicates that the overall usage profile in this study primarily reflects the experiences of lower-grade students. Riopel et al. (2019) show that outcomes from serious games vary across contexts. Tsai and Tsai (2020) likewise report that effects in digital game-based science learning are not uniform. Wang et al. (2022) finds similar variability for STEM achievement, so the study's grade-level composition should be kept in mind when interpreting the results.

Table 2. Gender of Student Respondents (N = 46)

Gender	n	%
Male	28	61
Female	18	39

The sample included more male than female respondents. Reporting gender composition clarifies whose perspectives are most represented in the descriptive profile and provides context for interpreting students' responses, particularly given that experiences with gamified activities may differ across learners and classroom cultures.

Table 3. Blooket Game Modes Used for Integrated Science Review (N = 46)

Game Mode	n	%
Gold Quest	37	80
Tower Defense	6	13
Battle Royale	7	15
Fishing Frenzy	12	26
Crazy Kingdom	5	11
Tower of Doom	0	0
Other (Crypto)	26	57

Note: Students could select more than one mode; therefore, percentages do not sum to 100%. Percentages use N = 46 as the denominator.

Mode use clustered in a small number of options. Gold Quest was the most frequently reported mode ($n = 37, 80\%$), and Crypto was also common ($n = 26, 57\%$); other modes were selected by smaller subsets, and Tower of Doom was not reported (0%). This pattern is substantively important because Blooket’s arcade-style modes draw on the same underlying question set but vary in mechanics and pacing, which changes how students encounter the review task in practice (Thu & Dan, 2023). Wenjing Huang (2022) similarly characterizes Blooket’s mode system as a core feature that differentiates the learning experience even when content remains constant. Accordingly, the perceptions documented in this study should be interpreted as reflecting the design affordances and constraints of the dominant modes used in this setting, rather than the full range of Blooket’s possible formats. This interpretation is consistent with STEM-oriented game-based learning scholarship emphasizing that learning outcomes and student experience are sensitive to design features and classroom implementation (Klopfer & Thompson, 2020). It also aligns with synthesis evidence that digital game-based learning effects in science and STEM are heterogeneous and contingent on how games are designed and enacted in context (Riopel et al., 2019; Tsai & Tsai, 2020; Wang et al., 2022).

Table 4. Teaming Format Used During Blooket Science Review (N= 42)

Teaming Format	n	%
Solo	32	76
Teams	5	12
Both Solo and Teams	5	12

Blooket review was implemented mainly as solo play (32 of 42 responses, 76.2%), with comparatively limited use of team-only and mixed solo–team formats (5 of 42 each, 12%). This implementation profile matters because participation structure shapes what students are invited to do during review. Solo formats typically position success around individual speed and accuracy, whereas team formats create more space for peer explanation, shared strategy, and learning through social interaction, which collaborative learning scholarship identifies as a key pathway for strengthening understanding (Hogan & Tudge, 2014). In that sense, the predominantly individual structure documented here provides an important interpretive frame for students’ later ratings on competition, collaboration, classroom climate, and fairness: their “Blooket experience” largely reflects an individually paced, performance-visible review routine rather than a consistently dialogic, peer-supported one. Reporting this context also responds to a limitation in much of the existing Blooket literature, which often relies on broad perception measures without closely specifying how the platform was enacted in the classroom (Susilo et al., 2022; Sartika et al., 2023; Kinanti & Sari, 2024; Isyimirahim et al., 2024).

Research Question 2: To what extent do students perceive Blooket as an effective science review tool?

This research question examined students’ perceptions of Blooket as a tool for integrated science review across eight dimensions: engagement, motivation, perceived learning and quiz readiness, feedback and metacognitive support, technical ease and access, competition/collaboration and classroom climate, fairness and alignment with science content, and overall acceptance and intention. Responses were recorded on a

5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Dimension scores are summarized using overall means and standard deviations.

Table 5. Overall Perception Ratings by Dimension (N = 46)

Dimension	Mean	SD
Engagement (attention, participation, persistence)	4	1
Motivation (interest/enjoyment, confidence)	4	1
Perceived Learning & Quiz Readiness (how it helps prepare for the quiz)	4	1
Feedback & Metacognition (instant feedback, strategy)	4	1
Technical Ease & Access (usability, joining, stability)	4	1
Competition, Collaboration & Classroom Climate	4	1
Fairness & Alignment with Science Content	4	1
Overall Acceptance & Intention	4	1

As shown in Table 5, students rated Blooket positively across all eight dimensions, with section means at the Agree level ($M = 4.00$) and comparable dispersion ($SD = 1.00$). This suggests that students' endorsement extended beyond enjoyment to review-relevant outcomes, including perceived quiz readiness, feedback support, usability, classroom climate, and content alignment. This pattern aligns with accounts of well-implemented game-based review as fostering interactive practice and sustained participation (Klopfer & Thompson, 2020; Ball et al., 2020) and with STEM-focused discussions of innovation that targets both engagement and learning processes (Kayan-Fadlelmula et al., 2022). At the same time, the shared SD indicates meaningful differences in endorsement strength across students, consistent with evidence that digital game-based learning outcomes vary with design and implementation conditions (Riopel et al., 2019). Similar variability is reported in meta-analyses of digital game-based science learning (Tsai & Tsai, 2020). Parallel conclusions appear in reviews of STEM achievement outcomes (Wang et al., 2022).

Because these are dimension-level summaries, they are best read as an overall perception profile rather than as proof that every feature worked equally well for every learner. The qualitative findings that follow therefore add needed specificity about which features students valued most and which conditions constrained the experience, echoing prior work noting that competitive pressure and access-related issues can shape Blooket evaluations (Thu & Dan, 2023; Nappe, 2023; Nabila & Nurhamidah, 2024).

Research Question 3: What benefits, challenges, and improvements do students report regarding Blooket for science review?

Students' open-ended responses were analyzed using a qualitative descriptive thematic approach to identify recurring benefits, challenges, and recommendations regarding Blooket for science review. Overall, students described Blooket as an engaging and practical review format, while also emphasizing that its usefulness depends on pacing, item design, and how competition is managed in class. This pattern aligns with synthesis evidence that DGBL outcomes are design- and context-dependent.

Benefits. Students most often emphasized engagement and sustained attention, describing Blooket as “*fun*” and focus-supporting (e.g., “*It’s fun,*” “*I was actually paying attention and I was locked in,*” and “*It helps me learn quicker and keeps my focus*”). They also valued immediate corrective feedback and learning from errors (e.g., “*It gives me the right answer when I got it wrong*” and “*It would tell me and I could fix my mistakes*”), consistent with

the role of timely feedback in technology-enhanced learning (Aisyah et al., 2024). Many students additionally highlighted repetition and perceived quiz relevance, noting that repeated exposure helped retention and readiness (e.g., *“The questions pop up multiple times... This helps because you learn the answer,”* and *“The questions are typically the same as the test”*), echoing emerging classroom evidence that Blooket can support motivation and understanding when used for review (Astuti, 2025). Some students also described motivational energy from competition and shared participation, such as *“everyone is trying to win the 1st place,”* which aligns with findings that gamification features can strengthen participation and effort when well implemented (Ball et al., 2020; Klopfer & Thompson, 2020; Kayan-Fadlelmula et al., 2022; Ishak et al., 2021).

Challenges. The most frequent concerns involved pacing. Students reported feeling rushed (e.g., *“I did not like the speed. I felt like I have to rush,”* *“Speed”*), suggesting that timed play can shift review from deliberate practice to quick responding for some learners. Others pointed to question design and limited explanatory support, often citing *“Question types,”* *“Some questions format,”* and *“Wrong answers has no explanations.”* These issues reflect broader cautions that game-based learning benefits are not automatic and may be reduced when design features add cognitive burden or do not support conceptual clarification (e.g., Wang et al., 2022). Social dynamics were mixed: while competition was motivating for many, some expressed discomfort or pressure (e.g., *“Competition... I don’t like it so much,”* *“Trying to stay in the first place”*), consistent with reports that competitive modes can be stressful or discouraging for some learners (Thu & Dan, 2023; Nappe, 2023; Nabila & Nurhamidah, 2024). A smaller set noted diminishing novelty (*“After doing it a while, it gets boring”*) and peer-related distractions (*“When someone takes my ... avatar”*).

Suggested improvements. Students’ recommendations directly targeted these constraints. The most common request was more time and pacing adjustment (*“More time to answer questions,”* *“Longer game sessions,”* and *“Just the amount of time to do the questions”*), and one student proposed reducing penalty pressure through retries (*“Give us two tries to answer before it counts against us”*). Students also asked for clearer items and explanations (*“Word the questions better,”* *“Changing the format... paragraphs would be better,”* and *“Add explanations”*). Others requested greater variety and flexibility in modes and participation formats (*“More gamemodes,”* *“Putting us in team sometimes,”* *“to allow me play alone”*) and additional practice opportunities (*“assign it for homework”*). These recommendations are consistent with ICT integration work emphasizing that technology’s learning value depends on teacher decisions about scaffolding, pacing, and how tools are embedded in instruction (Mahdum et al., 2019; Ningsih et al., 2021; Junaidi et al., 2020). Notably, several students indicated no changes were needed (*“Nothing”*), underscoring the variability in learner experience also observed in DGBL research (e.g., Tsai & Tsai, 2020).

Conclusion

This study examined secondary students’ experiences with Blooket for integrated science review. Overall, students reported consistently positive perceptions across engagement, motivation, perceived quiz readiness, feedback support, usability, classroom climate, fairness/alignment, and acceptance, with especially strong endorsement of Blooket as a good way to review and a tool they would use again. Qualitative responses converged with these patterns, emphasizing enjoyment, sustained focus, immediate corrective feedback, and repeated exposure to questions as

key benefits that supported confidence and preparation. At the same time, students identified clear implementation pressures—most notably time/speed demands, question format concerns, and a lack of explanations for incorrect answers; competition energized many but created stress or distraction for some.

These findings should be interpreted with several limitations in mind: the study relied on self-report data from a single setting, included no comparison group or objective outcome measures, and had stronger representation from lower grade levels. Practically, the results suggest that Blooket is most effective when teachers calibrate pacing, strengthen item clarity, and add brief explanation or debrief routines so feedback becomes instructionally useful; offering flexible formats (solo/team) and rotating modes may also help balance excitement with psychological comfort. Future research should expand to multiple sites, examine year-level differences more systematically, and pair perception data with performance indicators to clarify which design and implementation conditions best support science learning during review.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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